

INTENSIVE METHODS OF SILKWORM CULTIVATION THE IMPORTANCE OF SOIL FOR THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF MULBERRY SEEDLINGS**¹Valiev Sayfiddin Tojiddinovich, ²Sokhibova Nigora Sadritdinovna**¹Dr.Agr.Sci., senior researcher, Deputy director for scientific affairs at Sericulture research instituteEmail:nigorasokhibova1324@mail.com²Tashkent state agrarian university<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8354134>

Abstract. *This article examines the influence of intensive tutors on the composition of the soil, the climate of experimental agriculture and the air temperature in intensive tutors, where the schemes 1, 4X0,5 m, 1, 2x0, 22 m, 09x09 m are organized.*

Keywords: *soil, climate, air intake, yield, water, evaporation, mulberry leaf, yield, nutrient, intensive, scheme, cocoon, bundles, twig.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье исследуется влияние интенсивных репетиторов на состав почвы, климат экспериментального земледелия и температуру воздуха в интенсивных репетиторах, где организованы схемы 1, 4X0,5 м, 1, 2x0, 22 м, 09x09 м.*

Ключевые слова: *почва, климат, воздухозаборник, урожайность, вода, испарение, лист шелковицы, урожайность, питательная, интенсивная, схема, кокон, пучки, веточка.*

Introduction. Research work on the topic of research was carried out in 2019-2021 at the Department of silk and tobacco of the Tashkent State Agrarian University and the main field experiments at 0.30 hectares of the DUK experimental area of the Center for innovation in agriculture and consulting at the Tashkent State Agrarian University.

The Tashkent region, where the main field experiments were carried out, is located in the northeastern part of the Republic and includes the Western Tyan-Shan mountain and mountain regions, the valleys of the Angren and Chirchiq rivers. The provincial territory is located at Latitude 42°17' and longitude 40°15' North and longitude 68°39' and 71°2 ' East. The province borders the Republic of Kazakhstan to the North and Northwest, the Kyrgyz Republic to the east and South-East, the Republic of Tajikistan to the south, and the Sirdarya region of the Republic to the West.

Climate. The climatic conditions of the experimental area are sharply continental. Summers are hot, dry; winters are cold and snowy. The average summer temperature is 29.4°C in July and 4.5°C in January in winter. The average air humidity is 47% in July, 72% in December-January, and precipitation is 400-500 mm year-round, unevenly distributed throughout the seasons and months of the year.

According to the observations of the Institute meteostancy, the annual precipitation is 395.7 ml (see Figure 2.1).

Precipitation is high throughout the spring months, with a fat content of 210.6 ml, with the summer months in particular being dry and hot.

The average air temperature was +32.5 o C and the relative air humidity was 53 percent. In the second decade of July, the maximum air temperature was observed. The maximum air temperature was 41.5 o C, and the relative humidity of the air in August was 58 percent.

Even in September, the air temperature was warm, with an average temperature of +21.9 °C, a maximum temperature of 31.5 °C, a minimum temperature of +5 °C observed in the first and third decade of the month.

Figure 2.1. Air temperature indicators of Tashkent district, Tashkent region during the years of the study, °C, 2021.

The amount of precipitation this month was 72% of the relative humidity of 35.7 ml of air.

The sharp drop in air temperature began from the second decade of October, the minimum air temperature in the second decade was 2.5 os, the relative humidity of the air was 72 percent, the minimum above-ground air temperature indicator fell to 2.0 o C.

During the period of research, seasonal weather conditions became favorable for the growth and development of the mulberry plant. Due to the lack of moisture, irrigation was eliminated through artificial ditches.

Figure 2.2. In the years of the study, the indicators of the annual amount of precipitation in the cross section of the Kibray District of the Tashkent region by month 2021 year.

The duration of sunlight in Kibray district, where the Experimental Station is located, averages 2,893 hours per year. In the summer season, it reaches up to 362-396 hours in one month, and in winter it averages 103-127 hours. The average overnight temperature variation amplitude reaches 25-31^os in January and July.

The coldest months of the Kibray district climate are December, January and February. A minimum temperature of -13.5^o s has been observed in certain years. Snowy days are observed in the December-February season, the snow cover is thick and unstable, its average thickness is around 3-5 cm.

Early spring is characterized by frequent return of frosts as well as late spring frosty days. In this case, special attention should be paid to the growth and development of mulberry plants.

The most precipitation in the district is observed in April and November. The minimum amount of atmospheric precipitation falls mainly during the summer months, which makes it convenient when growing a mulberry plant. Soil composition: the soil of the DUK experimental area of the Center for innovation development and Consulting in agriculture under the Tashkent State Agrarian University is included in the irrigated typical rich soil, it is known. according to the mechanical composition of heavy sand - 53.1, the upper part of the section (profile) of irrigated coarse soils, the layer thickness, is formed from agro irrigation layers equal to 05-1 m. They are characterized by high porosity and water permeability, as well as high biological activity. The formation conditions of the amount of humus in this soil fluctuate in amounts ranging from 0.5-1.7%, depending on the watering period and the degree of washing (see Table 2.1).

Figure 2.3. Overview of the experimental field

In the soil of the experimental field, humus – 1,710% (determined by the level of supply).

Mobile phosphorus (P₂O₅) contains 70.1 mg/kg (very high) in the surface layer of soil and -18.3 (low) in the soil pasatki layer, alternating potassium (K₂O) 408.6 mg/kg in the surface layer of soil and 240.2 mg/kg (medium) in the bottom layer of soil, carbonates (HCO₂) in the surface layer of soil-0.038% (good), chlorine (Cl) in soil-0.006% (unsalinated), sulfate (SO₄)

content-0.023%, calcium (sa)-0.008% (very low), magnesium (mg) – 0.003% (very low) and RN-7.10 neutral.

Table 3.**Results of chemical analysis of the soil of the experimental area.**

№	№	№	humus,	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
	Cross section	Leyer	%	mg/kg	mg/kg
1	1	0-20	1,710	70,1	408,6
2		20-40	1,014	19,2	263,8
3		40-60	0,712	18,3	240,2
4	2	0-20	1,348	29,1	277,6
5		20-40	0,951	25,9	227,9
6		40-60	0,824	13,8	216,3
7	3	0-20	1,410	46,2	395,7
8		20-40	1,124	24,1	227,9
9		40-60	0,994	18,3	204,8
10	4	0-20	1,391	50,0	410,6
11		20-40	1,179	37,2	253,7
12		40-60	0,910	14,3	220,4
13	5	0-20	1,669	52,5	382,3
14		20-40	1,388	44,0	251,6
15		40-60	1,160	17,4	244,8

Table 4.**Mechanical composition of experimental field soil**

Cross section	Leyer, sm.	Fractions, %							Physical blur, %
		0,25	0,25-0,1	0,1-0,5	0,05-0,01	0,01-0,005	0,005-0,001	0,001	
1	0-20	0,9	0,4	8,1	39,7				51,7
	20-40	0,7	0,4	6,7	41,2				51,2
	40-60	0,5	0,3	7,0	42,0				50,6
2	0-20	0,5	0,4	6,9	39,7				52,3
	20-40	0,6	0,4	7,6	39,3				51,2
	40-60	0,6	0,4	7,7	39,1				51,5
3	0-20	0,6	0,3	6,9	40,3				51,2
	20-40	0,6	0,4	6,9	36,4				52,1
	40-60	0,4	0,3	7,9	39,1				52,2
4	0-20	0,4	0,4	7,8	35,1				52,1
	20-40	0,4	0,4	7,8	34,3				52,0
	40-60	0,4	0,3	8,8	33,3				53,1
5	0-20	0,5	0,4	7,8	35,1				52,0
	20-40	0,4	0,4	7,8	34,0				52,1
	40-60	0,4	0,3	8,8	35,1				52,4

The soil of the experimental site is not rich in organic matter. In terms of the amount of mobile forms of nitrogen, the soil is considered to be very low and poor, high in phosphorus, low and moderate in potassium.

The soil of the experimental field is moderately supplied with trace elements. The amount of absorbent shaly elements in it (in relation to mg/kg of soil) is as follows: boron – 0.23-0.28; copper – 0.20-0.62, molybdenum – 0.22-0.72, manganese – 35.4-42.

Conclusion

Based on the above data, it can be concluded that the availability of information about the composition of the soil before any experiment is the reason for the high yield of leaves obtained during intensive cultivation.

REFERENCES

1. Sokhibova N S Nazirova M.I Solieva M B “Influence of rearing silk worms with productive mulberry leaves on the biological indicators of silk gland and raw silk effectiveness”, Life Sciences and Agriculture Б.87-90 ISSN2181-0761. -ISSN2181-0761, 2020-yil. [doi: 10.24411/2181- 0761/2020-10032](https://doi.org/10.24411/2181-0761/2020-10032).
2. Vakhobdzhan K. Rahmonberdiev, Nigora S. Sohibova, Murodjon M. Nurov, Durdon B. Alikulova “Study of the chemical composition of the spring leaf and the productivity of mulberry varieties in the conditions of the navai region steppe” European international journal of multidisciplinary research and management studies. -issn: 2750-8587 2022-yil. [doi: https://doi.org/10.55640/eijmrms-02-05-28](https://doi.org/10.55640/eijmrms-02-05-28)
3. Sokhibova, Umida U. Khaknazarova, Tursun Sh. Ibragimov, Nilufar S. Abduganieva “Studying the economic characteristics of mulberry seedlings propagated in a new way in the tashkent region”, European international journal of multidisciplinary research and management studies. -issn: 2750-8587, 2022-yil. [doi: https://doi.org/10.55640/eijmrms-02-06-20](https://doi.org/10.55640/eijmrms-02-06-20)
4. S. Purusothaman, S. Muthuvelu, U. Balasubramanian va P. Murugesan. Biochemical Analysis of Mulberry Leaves (*Morus alba* L.) and Silkworm *Bombyx mori* Enriched with Vermiwash, 2012. 9: 289-295. [doi: 10.3923/je.2012.289.295](https://doi.org/10.3923/je.2012.289.295)
5. Tang C., Luo G., Wang Z., Dai F. Breeding and diversified utilization research on polyploid hybrid mulberry variety Yuesang 11. //8th Black, Caspian Seas and Central Asia Silk Association (BACSA) INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE «Climate changes and chemicals – the new + challenges» «CLISERI» 2017. Sheki, Azerbaijan. April 2nd – 7th 2017. P 19-6.